

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Corrosion resistance of friction stir welded AA6082-T651 Al alloy

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There are several commercially utilized technologies for joining of aluminium alloys. Most common approaches are conventional arc welding methods. However, these techniques may cause problems with deformation of the structures due to the thermal cycle during welding and even 50% lower mechanical properties. Recently, Friction Stir Welding (FSW) method is being actively developed as a possible alternative for conventional arc methods. The FSW method utilizes the rotary and sliding motion of the tool to heat, plasticize, and weld the joined materials. The obtained fine-grained structure of FSW joints results in up to 95% of the strength of the parent material. The FSW process creates three characteristic regions in the material: the retreading side, the advancing side, and the weld. Each of them is characterized by different microstructure and mechanical properties.

Another important parameter on the way of a wide commercial application of FSW technique is the corrosion resistance of the welds, which is an important parameter during the exploitation of Al structures in technological and aerospace applications. Currently, there is a significant gap in the scientific literature on the examination of corrosion propensity of particular regions of FSW joints. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to examine the corrosion resistance of three characteristic regions of the friction stir welded Al alloy and correlate it with their microstructure and local surface electrochemical properties.

The weld made of two plates of AA6082-T651 Al alloy (Al-Mg-Si type) was examined. The examined areas were the retreading side, the advancing side, the middle area of the weld, and the base material as a reference. The microstructure evaluation of the formed weld included scanning electron microscopy with the elemental and electron backscatter diffraction analysis. The surface local Volta potential differences were monitored by the scanning Kelvin probe force microscopy (SKPFM). Corrosion experiments were performed in 3.5% NaCl solution included classical and dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, polarization resistance measurements and potentiodynamic polarization.

The results showed that the performed welding did not affect the chemical composition of the joint while resulted in the formation of a fine-grade microstructure. The SKPFM measurements confirmed that the alloying elements formed different types of intermetallic particles (IMPs) in the microstructure of all examined areas. The Al(Si, Fe, Mn) IMPs were of cathodic nature, while the Mg-rich particles showed the anodic behaviour, confirming susceptibility of this alloy to local corrosion. The predominant local corrosion attack was then confirmed in the corrosion experiments in 3.5% NaCl solution. The corrosion resistance of the examined areas decreased in a row: retreading side → base material → middle of the weld → advancing side. The results were supported by the proposed corrosion mechanisms.

The performed experiments contributed to the understanding of the corrosion resistance of particular areas of FSW-welded aluminium alloys on the way for the wider commercial utilization of this technique.

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